

ATTITUDE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TOWARDS THE USE OF COMPUTERS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to examine the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the use of computer in education. A sample of 50 secondary school teachers was assessed for their attitude towards the use to computers using the 5 point Likert scale adopted by Albirini with certain modification. The result of this study showed that there is significant difference in secondary school teacher's attitude towards the use of computers in education with respect to their age. The findings have implications for the teachers to equip themselves through computers literacy trainings. Government has to provide infrastructure facilities for use of computers in classrooms. Thus the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the use of computers in education can be improved.

Index Terms: Attitude, Secondary School Teachers & Use of Computers in Education.

1. Introduction:

Computer has emerged as one of the most important aspect of human life. Computer during the past three decades especially after the advent of the internet have transformed the way we communicate, the way we conduct business and the way we entertain ourselves. In education field it has affected every aspects of school working including administration, timetable, lesson delivery, project work, evaluation, examination system etc... Computers have made teaching learning process more relevant for the learner and connected to real life. It is generally accepted as the modern instrumental tool which enables the teachers to modify the teaching methods they use in order to enhance the students interest. In India there is serious need for increasing the learning abilities of the students with the help of computers. The teacher is key to effective implementation of the use of computers in the educational system. Teachers have tremendous potential to transmit beliefs and values of students. So, the teacher's attitude towards the use computers results upon the computers usage in school.

Attitude is defined by Ajzen (2005) as a disposition to respond favorably or unfavorably to on object, person, institution or event (P.3). In this theory of planned behavior Ajzen (1988, 2005) linked attitude and behavior through the description of three types of belief system that guide human behavior namely behavioral beliefs, normative beliefs and control belief.

Attitudes are key factors in whether teachers accept computer as a teaching tool in their teaching practice. A number of studies were carried out to determine teacher's attitude towards use of computer. Harrison and Rainer (1992) conducted their research using data compiled from a 1990 survey of 776 knowledge and information workers from large university in the Southern United States. They found that participants with negative computer attitude were less skilled in computer use and were therefore less likely to accept computers use and adapt to technology those with positive attitude. Albirni (2004) conducted a study to investigate the attitude of EFL teachers in education. He found that teachers have positive attitude towards technology use in education Hountz and Gupta (2001) found that male and female had rated themselves on their ability to use the computer is significantly in different ways.

Other studies have suggested that the masculine image of the computer has deterred females from benefiting from the technology and this has made them less confident or more anxious (Culley 1988) resulting in females holding more negative attitudes to computers than males (Cambell 1990). (On squinty, female students tends to use computers less even when given equal access (Muir-1987). The research on gender and composting has after reported, though not conclusively, that males have more experience and make more use of computers. (Brosnath & Lee, 1998, Balka and Smith 2000)

2. Need and Significance of the Study:

A Number of studies were carried out to determine teacher's attitude towards the use of computers in education with respect of their gender. But the investigator has not found any study on teacher's attitude towards the use of computers in education with respect to their age group. So the investigator aimed at assessing the teacher's attitude towards the use of computers in education with respect to their age. In the present study the investigator has taken the teachers of below 40 years and above 40 years to study the use of computers in education. Because both age group of teachers play dual role in education activity. They play the role of teaching as well as the role of guiding students. So their effects their on the use of computers in education.

3. Statement of the Problem:

A study on attitude of secondary school teachers towards the use of computers in education with respect to their age.

4. Objective:

- ✓ To study the attitude of secondary school teachers of below 40 years towards the use of computers.
- ✓ To study the attitude of secondary school teachers of above 40 years towards the use of computers in education.
- ✓ To study the difference in attitude of secondary school teachers towards the use of computers with respect to their age.

5. Operational Definitions:

Attitude: Positive and Negative emotional reactions of secondary school teachers towards the use of computers in education.

Secondary School Teachers: Teachers who teach from 8th std to 10th std in Puttur Tq.

Education: Teaching learning process in secondary schools.

Computer Use: Use of computers in maintaining teacher's records and use in classroom activities.

6. Hypothesis:

There is significance difference in attitude of secondary school teachers towards the use of computers with respect to their age.

7. Methodology:

The present study is a descriptive survey undertaken to study the attitude of secondary school teachers towards the use of computers with respect to their age. Population consisted of all the secondary school teachers of Puttur Taluk. The sample of the study consisted of 50 secondary school teachers of below 40 and above 40 years of age. A 5 point Likert scale developed by Albirini (2006) was used with some modification to measure the teacher's attitude towards the use of computer in education.

8. Objective One: The first objective was to study the attitude or secondary school teachers of below 40 years age towards the use of computers in education. The

objective was analyzed using Descriptive Statistics, namely, Mean and SD. The result of the test are given below.

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Attitude of secondary school teachers of below 40 years age.	25	36.7	4.8

9. Objective Two: The second objective was to study the attitude of secondary school teachers of above 40 years age.

Variable	N	Mean	SD
Attitude of secondary school teachers of above 40 years age.	25	29.1	6.6

10. Objective Three: To study the difference in attitude of secondary school teachers of below and above 40 years towards the use of computers in education.

Variable	Status	N	M	SD	T Value	Result
Attitude of secondary school teachers	Below 40 years	25	36.7	4.8	5.18	Significant 0.05 level
	Above 40 years	25	29.1	6.6		

11. Major Findings:

This study reveals that there is significant difference in attitude of secondary school teachers below and above 40 years age towards the use of computers in education. Teachers below 40 years have more positive attitude than teachers of above 40 years and thus they use computers in education more effectively.

12. Educational Implications:

Teacher's attitude towards use of computers plays significant role in education and develop positive attitude, there is a need of training in the use of computers especially for the teachers of above 40 years age.

- ✓ Computer labs and classrooms must be equipped with appropriate computers making way for SMART classes. It influences the teachers to have positive attitude towards computers use in education.
- ✓ Government must draft policy to assist states in making optional use of computers in school education.
- ✓ Introduction ICT in of curriculum school must be done mandatory. It will encourage teaching learning activity.
- ✓ Government must provide computers or lap tops to the teachers or without any cost.

13. Conclusion:

Having a positive attitude towards use of computers in education is a growing concern for present day. In this age of technology, it is the teachers who are responsible for educating the future generation. In order to discharge the responsibility at desired level teachers must prepare themselves for future. For this purpose they need to develop and update themselves constantly. The aim of this study was to examine the attitude of school teachers towards use of computers in education. Through analyzing the data and financially results the investigator concluded that teachers of secondary schools differ in their attitude towards the use of computers in education with respect to their age.

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